

Supplemental Figure 2. Sample raw data traces. Representative raw data traces from a single participant at sea level. Rebreathing tests are performed twice, once at a hyperoxic oxygen level ($F_{IO_2}=30\%$ sea-level equivalent), and once at a hypoxic oxygen level ($P_{ETO_2} = 50$ mmHg).